

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 15 (2022)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2022,
vol. 15

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES VIA ONLINE LEARNING: HOW HAS BASIC SCHOOLING RESPONDED TO COVID-19: A SOUTH AFRICAN PERSPECTIVE

PS Zubane¹, SH Khoza², Victor H Mlambo³

Abstract

In South Africa, The COVID-19 pandemic and its subsequent disruption of the social order adversely affected the deliverance of education, thus compromising the future of millions of young people and the socio-economic development of the country itself. The sudden and rushed transition from physical contact classes to online learning has revealed the extent to which South Africa's basic education system is unprepared for possible disruptions. This paper examines whether sudden and rushed transition from physical contact classes to online learning can be seen as a barrier to inclusive education, especially considering the inequalities in South Africa's basic education system. Additionally, while the paper acknowledges that the pandemic has negatively affected the country's primary schooling, it also seeks to examine how the South African government has responded to this disruption. This paper adopted a qualitative research approach and the review of the literature was undertaken to answer the guiding questions of this paper. The socio-cultural theory was adopted to explain how education takes place within the social space, and how changes to that effect tend to influence teaching and learning. The paper reveals that South Africa's basic education system is not ready to fully implement online learning as there are considerable challenges that need to be addressed before this could be undertaken. This however is not unique to South Africa as developing countries are all finding it difficult to migrate from physical to online classes and sadly, it is young people who are disadvantaged in the process. This paper concludes that it is necessary for South Africa's basic education

1 University of Zululand: Department of History, zubanephephelo@yahoo.com

2 University of Zululand: Department of History, sekwenelekhoza@gmail.com

3 Ph.d. Victor H Mlambo, Lecturer, University of Johannesburg, School of Public Management, Governance & Public Policy, South Africa

system to prepare for possible disruptions in the future and ensure that such disruptions have minimal impact on learners.

Key Words: Online learning, Covid-19, South Africa, education

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic found its way to South Africa on the 5th of March 2020. News of the pandemic caused panic, fear and anxiety amongst South Africans. A 2020 survey by the South African Depression and Anxiety Group (SADAG) revealed that 55 percent of South Africans had feelings of anxiety and panic and 46 percent were under financial stress (Kaylynn, 2020). It became important that South Africa's response to the pandemic mirrored that of its global counterparts, which was underpinned by the need to stop the spread of the pandemic at all costs. Consequently, within the context of basic education, hard decisions had to be made; one of these was the need to move away from physical classes and incorporate online learning. Despite concerns that the Department of education lacks the required resources to undertake such, COVID-19 demanded that adjustments be made in a short space of time. Moll et al (2007) define e-Learning as 'flexible learning using ICT (Information and communications technology) resources, tools and applications, focusing on accessing information, interaction among teachers, learners, and the online environment collaborative learning, and production of resources and learning experiences. Acknowledging the above definition, Mlitwa and Van Belle (2011) explained that eLearning is the use of technological interventions for teaching, learning and assessment. With the above definitions, the South African government was under immense pressure to adjust and cope with the pandemic and also ensure that basic schooling was not brought to a complete standstill. While multiparty politics was consolidated in 1994, South Africa has failed to break free from the crippling chains of apartheid and its legacies. Arguably, land dispossession and apartheid legislation such as the Group Areas Act contributed to the skewed accessibility and education in South Africa evident by the considerable number of pupils who attend rural schools which have failed to be on par with their urban counterparts (Zhang, 2006). It is without a doubt that there's a technological divide between urban and rural schooling, hence this paper examines this divide and discusses how this divide perpetuates inequality within the realms of basic education. For the purpose of this paper, basic schooling is limited to public sector schools (Government-owned),

however, the paper does draw parallels between public and private schools for a robust analysis. As a point of departure, this paper argues that while South Africa may need to expedite its digital infrastructure development in order to consolidate the much-needed shift towards online Learning, socio-economic disparities which, to some extent contribute largely to the lack of skilled personnel in the country, the rurality of basic education; telecommunication issues and the divide between urban and rural area, will frustrate the process going forward.

Methodological issues

The study relied on secondary sources in collecting data regarding the topic under examination. It employed a review of the literature to understand how the South African government responded to the sudden change from physical face to face classes to online learning, the challenges associated with such and the implications thereof. The reason for this approach was to put into context the factors underpinning the massive digital divide in the country.

Literature Review

COVID-19: A South African Perspective

The advent of the Covid-19 pandemic was intensified by the unprecedented rate of infection throughout the country. While recorded cases remain active, the following graph indicates the geographic spread of the virus across the country as 24 October 2021.

Figure 1: Confirmed coronavirus (COVID-19) cases in South Africa, by Province

Source: Statista, 2021

Since the first reported case in March 2020, the number of those being infected increased to a point where the government introduced stringent measures to curb the spread of the virus. These were not undertaken in isolation, rather they mirrored a global response to the pandemic. Measures included a hard-national Lockdown which was done to prevent unnecessary movement. South Africa had lockdown from levels from 1 to 5, in which Lockdown level 5 in South Africa was deemed one the harshest in the World. Citizens weren't allowed to leave their residence except for essential purposes such as grocery shopping and medical care and had to have a permit permitting them to undertake such movement. All non-essential businesses and schools were shut down (Smart et al, 2020). The lockdown, as strict as it was, did not suffice as an adequate strategy. There was no decline in either daily new cases or deaths by March 27, which was the first day of level 5; and the latter part of July, this was when cases began to tail off during level 3 (Smart et al, 2020). In light of the foregoing statistics, it is worth noting that the COVID-19

virus had relatively little effect on children under 19 years. The Health Department (2020) also indicated that the age group between 10 and 19 accounted for 1 147 (4.2%) of the overall number of COVID-19 cases in the country. The number of cases for children accounted for 2.8% of the total number of cases, which then stood at 324 221 in the country and this can be linked to various factors such as genetics and age (Richards, 2020). Additionally, it was argued that their innate immune system and adaptive immune response played a huge role, where the body recognises the virus during the incubation period and eliminates it (Mahimbo et al., 2020). Among the known terms generally used to diagnose the virus (Asymptomatic, Mild, Moderate, Severe, Critical), most people who are young and healthy are likely to be asymptomatic or mild. Data from the World Health Organization (2020) suggests that as of 18 September 2020, children under the age of 18 years represent about 8.5% of reported cases, with relatively few deaths compared to other age groups. Medical Express (2020) reinforced the latter and argued that people under the age of 20 are half as likely to contract COVID-19 than the rest of the population. Looking at the COVID trajectory in South Africa, one would concede with the foregoing evidence.

Teachers and Pupils in School

Notably, the small percentile for the age group between 9 to 19 years is the age category that primary & secondary education learners fall under. However, as the department embarked on a phase-based approach to reopening schools, basic Education Minister Angie Motshekga reported that within a month, eleven teachers and 3 pupils had lost their lives nationally, while also reporting that 2 740 teachers (less than 1 percent of the total number employed in the sector) had been infected with the virus. Among learners, there were 1 260 reported infections with the highest number of infections coming from the Western Cape, Gauteng and Eastern Cape. The department introduced numerous measures to try and make up for the time lost owing to the lockdown. These included the rotation or platooning approach, adjusting the school calendar and introducing extra classes amongst others.

Second Wave

The COVID-19 remained a problem of great concern in South Africa throughout the year 2020. After the first wave peaked in July and August, the daily total for new cases fell dramatically. However, the number of new infections began to rise steeply at the beginning of

December, reaching 11,000 in daily reported cases just before the 24th of December (Burker, 2020). There seemingly was a positive link between the mutation of the commonly known COVID-19 virus and the sharp increase in infection rates in the country. First identified in Nelson Mandela Bay in October. The new variant, referred to as 501.V2, was discovered by a network of scientists around South Africa who have been tracking the genetics of the SARS-COV-2 virus. Since then, it has been reported that between 80% and 90% of new cases in the country were carrying the mutant variant, according to health authorities (Toyana, 2020). Prof Salim Abdool Karim, the chairman of the government's ministerial advisory committee (MAC) in 2020, stated that "It is still very early but at this stage, the preliminary data suggests the virus that is now dominating in the second wave is spreading faster than the first wave," (Burker, 2020). South Africa as of 24 October 2021 recorded a total of 2,919,632 cases of COVID-19, with almost 5 million deaths, according to official statistics. Excess mortality studies suggest a death toll of more than 56,000 (Burker, 2020). One may argue that given the manifestation of the virus, and its ability to evolve and the absence of a guaranteed preventative measure, the need for online learning remains a necessary adjustment that must be made at some point.

In Schools' Government response to Covid-19

Despite reporting accumulative numbers of cases across all provinces, the South African government was commended by international organisations such as the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), World Health Organizations (WHO) for its handling of the pandemic. President Cyril Ramaphosa was also instrumental in ensuring Africa is not left behind, especially concerning vaccine procurement (Vandome, 2020). In SA, as the infection rate began to increase, the governments' immediate response citing international examples such as Italy, Australia and New Zealand was to put the country on lockdown on the 27th of March 2020. International travel was restricted, campaigns raising awareness of the virus were intensified, going to work became a concern, public gatherings and the unnecessary movement of people were restricted, leading to a complete shutdown of public transport and schools across the country (Gustafsson, 2020). Accordingly, South Africa's basic education department had to navigate its way around the new reality and its implications thereafter. At the heart of the issue, was to find a quick answer to the question -how best to

ensure educational continuity, amid the rampant COVID-19 pandemic?

Learner support interventions

The department urgently needed to find new solutions to cope with the effects of the pandemic on basic schooling. The minister of basic education Angie Motshekga explained that the department used one-hundred and twenty-three (123) radio stations, and six (6) different television channels with a total reach of more than thirty-five (35) million people. This was made possible through the COVID-19 Learner Support Programme (LSP), an initiative that was aimed at limiting the impact of the lockdown on the school calendar. However, the core intention of the COVID-19 LSP was to provide school support to learners through bringing curriculum lessons to their respective households across the country since face to face classes were suspended. The initiative was part of the government's broader efforts to prevent a total loss of the school year owing to the lockdown (Motshekga, 2020). The government also made available resources online for those who can access such material. In their report on the School Recovery Plan in Response to COVID-19, guided by the principle of inclusion and equity, the Department of Basic Education (DBE) promised to "ensure that all learners, and particularly the most vulnerable, access the planned programs to ensure that no one gets left behind" (Department of Basic Education Report, 2020:8). Consequently, the government further introduced zero-rated platforms (Educational websites that could be accessed without mobile data), which carried curriculum content for use. This was vital especially for those learners who lived in rural areas and lacked stable internet connectivity. These interventions according to the minister were necessary measures to close the vacuum and reduce the educational inequality that would exist in future as a result of the COVID-19 lockdown. However, the effectiveness of these measures has been cast into doubt given the unfavourable socio-economic realities in South Africa. The economic and skills disparities in the country poses a great challenge to the effectiveness of the above-mentioned interventions. Among these challenges is the issue of the digital divide that is still deeply rooted not only in South African communities but in Africa as a whole. O'Shaughnessy and Stadler (2008) define the digital divide as the increasing access gap between those who have access to technology, access to content, information communication technology skills, and money to pay for digital services against those who do not. The digital divide is more

often used to refer to the difference between the developed and developing world's access to the benefits of digital technology (O'Shaughnessy and Staller, 2008). South Africa is still characterised by a significant digital divide in terms of information communication technologies possession, access, and use (Burger and Sinha, 2012). Additionally, there also exists a racial, socioeconomic, and geographical divide that has a direct link to apartheid. Generally, there is a significant number of South Africans who do not have the required skills to make use of new technologies and services owing to a lack of education and exposure to technologies (Research ICT Africa and Intelecon, 2012). The pace of the adoption of new technologies in South Africa is also still very slow compared to other developing nations such as Russia, Brazil and India. Furthermore, the 2018 Statistics South Africa's general household survey revealed that only 10.4% of the South African population had access to the internet. Walkers (2019) stated that while 17.3% of households in metropolitan areas had access to the internet at home, only 1.7% in rural areas had access. Given the latter, one may argue that in a developing country like South Africa where the digital divide is still prevalent, any intervention program that requires online digital communication technologies and platforms is likely to preclude learners located in rural areas, thus contributing to educational inequality. A study by Gulati (2008) reviewed the integration of Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) in different developing nations. The study showed that there is potential for e-learning initiatives to develop the education sector in these countries. However, poverty and lack of ICT infrastructure are the main issues that need to be addressed before such can become realisable.

Phase-based reopening of schools

Pending the search for "safer" alternatives to the traditional classroom-based environment, the minister announced the government's decision to tactically reopen schools. This entailed a phase-based approach, allowing Grade 7s and 12s back to school on the 8th of June 2020, as South Africa entered lockdown level 3. Other students were expected to return from 6 July, while the remainder of learners were expected to return from 3rd of August (Writer, 2020), however, some setbacks affected this plan. According to the government gazette, the phased reopening was carried out as follows: On July 6, 2020, Grades R, 1, 2, 3, 6, 10, and 11 would return. Schools for learners with Severe Intellectual Disabilities (SID) would welcome back learners of Grades R, 1, 2, 3, and final year.

Finally, Schools with autistic learners would reopen for the Junior Group (those below 13 years of age) and final year (those 18-years-old and above). On August 3, 2020, Grades 4, 5, 8, and 9 would return. Schools for learners with Severe Intellectual Disabilities (SID) would welcome back learners of Grades 4 and 5. Schools with autistic learners would reopen for the Senior Group (those 13-years-old and above). This approach by the department received criticism from multiple fronts. On May 29 2020, the Educators Union of South Africa (EUSA) approached the Gauteng High Court to file an urgent interdict against the department of basic education's plan to reopen schools, naming basic education minister Angie Motshekga as the respondent.

While the hearing was scheduled for the 2nd of June 2020, the judge postponed the matter till the 9 June, "stating that the department (of basic education) was not ready to proceed and that he needed more time to familiarize himself with the matter" (Kulkarni, 2020). The general secretary of the EUSA Siphwe Mpungose argued that "This is a matter of life and death and it is playing out in the media, while the rate of those being infected was increasing, the decision to reopen the schools was rushed to benefit suppliers of personal protective equipment (PPE) school nutrition programmes and scholar transport operations". Mpungose argued that the unplanned return of teachers, pupils and support staff before appropriate safety measures are in place would exacerbate the situation, citing issues such as water shortages and pit toilets at some schools, as well as student transport-related issues (Venter, 2020). The foregoing argument speaks to the lack of infrastructure in most of the schools in rural areas across the country. Between May 16-18, 2020, the Professional Educators' Union (PEU), South African Teachers' Union (SAOU), National Professional Teachers' Organisation of South Africa (NAPTOSA), South African Democratic Teachers Union (SADTU) and the National Teachers Union (NATU) undertook a survey that would reveal the readiness of schools for reopening regarding compliance across the country. Of the 9,365 schools which responded to the survey from all the nine provinces, the findings revealed that 92% of schools reported that they do not have material for cleaning and disinfecting the premises daily; 78% of schools reported that sanitation facilities do not have soap and water; 42% of the schools are dependent on water tanks for the supply of water and 39% have not received this supply from the government (Peoples Dispatch, 2020). While opposition parties such as the Democratic Party (DA), welcomed the move to reopen schools in phases, there

were reservations about concerns around the capacity to implement the outlined safety requirements in time. Freedom Front Plus (FFP), and the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF) also raised concerns over the opening of schools, citing poor levels of sanitation, especially in rural-based schools.

In school safety measures for COVID-19

The government was adamant about disinfecting all schools in time before the phased return of learners began. The department of basic education sent a document to schools outlining the standard operating procedure during the lockdown. The document also contained rules for all learners, educators, support staff, officials, parents and communities, the document detailed the need to avoid gatherings; maintain a social distance of at least 1.5-2 metres between peoples, where possible; every learner, staff member and visitor must wear a cloth mask at all times; avoid direct contact with others e.g. shaking hands or hugging; frequently wash hands with water and soap; avoid touching the face (i.e. eyes, nose, and mouth) with unwashed hands and eradicate all forms of stigma and discrimination as a result of Covid-19 (Writer, 2020). Orientation programmes for principals, school management teams (SMTs), non-teaching staff and teachers were developed, provincialised and targeted officials from provincial departments and district offices, training principals and school staff (South African Government, 2020).

The provincial education department identified about three thousand, five hundred (3 500) schools with water supply challenges. While some schools had existing on-site storage tanks, several schools did not have on-site storage tanks. Rand Water, contracted by the department, assisted with the procurement and delivery of additional on-site storage tanks and water supplies. Municipalities came on board, as part of the cooperation between the Department of Basic Education (DBE) the Department of Cooperative Governance and Traditional Affairs (COGTA), the South African Local Government Association (SALGA) and the Municipal Infrastructure Support Agent (MISA). Tanks were delivered to an additional two thousand, one hundred and seventy-five (2 175) schools. In terms of sanitation, the minister reported that in the Eastern Cape, all nine hundred and ten (910) schools requiring proper sanitation, also had received proper sanitation. In Limpopo, all four hundred and fifty-three (453) schools requiring proper sanitation, had proper sanitation (South African Government 2020).

Barriers and Opportunities associated with Online learning in South Africa

The pandemic has changed how education is delivered, let alone accessed. Because of the rapid growth of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), online learning has become a prominent feature in the education sector. It has been argued that eLearning enables learners to improve problem-solving skills and empowers educators to disseminate and impart knowledge effectively (Mlitwa & Van Belle, 2011). Accordingly, the shift from traditional face-face classes to online learning eliminates all barriers associated with the classroom environment, however, it also gives rise to new barriers to inclusive learning. In the digital world teaching and learning can occur anywhere, anytime and at any pace (Microsoft in Education, 2014), where learners would not have to be confined to the classroom, thus eliminating present challenges such as congested classrooms and lack of infrastructure. Online learning can address the congested class dilemma by providing accessible content regardless of location; by promoting personalised learning (Bagarukayo & Kalema, 2015). According to Emmanuel (2013), the OECD (2011) and Skelton (2014), infrastructure provision has a great impact on the quality of education and is one of the most important factors to take into consideration when measuring academic performance in schools. Overcrowded classrooms are also believed by Van Wyk (2008) to be a contributing factor to poor learning conditions because of the lack of space, fresh air and high noise levels that could lead to a lack of attention and focus.

However, while online learning mitigates the congestion classroom dilemma, online accessibility-inequality arises. While other challenges to online learning include negative eLearning perceptions, where learners might not be familiar or educated about what eLearning is and may not be fully receptive of it, lack/scarcie resources such as not having a laptop, tablet or a smartphone remain major barriers to online learning in the country (Venter et al. 2012). As cited prior, socio-economic disparities remain a topical subject, and a very unfortunate reality for most South Africans in the country, the vast majority fail to match high internet costs and fail to pass the affordability test required to facilitate online learning (Isabirye & Dlodlo, 2014). Learners residing in the deep rural areas are frustrated by poor network services as opposed to their urban-based counterparts (Jaffer et al, 2007). Sadly, Jantjies (2020) posited that before the pandemic, many teachers in the country had not received substantive formal training on the use of remote technology

in teaching and learning, either to support blended teaching and learning or to fully apply online learning. The decision by the Ministry of Basic Education to shut down schools in response to the pandemic forced teachers to adapt and become innovative to ensure that learning continued despite the challenges faced. Additionally, online learners have a greater tendency to demand multitask. Multitasking behaviour and distraction can compromise the effectiveness of online classes. Learner attention and focus are distracted by texting, answering emails, chatting on Facebook or WhatsApp, watching videos on YouTube, browsing on Google, or listening to music while at the same time participating in an online class. These distractions take the already emotionally absent students away from their learning objectives (Edwiser, 2020). A study by Abbasi et al (2020) reveals that the majority of the student's preferred face to face teaching over e-teaching. The key finding of the study showed that the students are not yet ready for e-learning. Czerniewicz et al (2006) noted that one of the opportunities associated with online learning is that the population will get to understand technology to convert and support learning cognition and meta-cognition. eLearning promotes learner-centred learning and enhances activities that promote collaboration, communication and interaction, and gives learners a better experience (Du et al, 2013). It also enables learners to apply knowledge in novel situations through case studies, role-playing and simulations. The pandemic had shone a light on the gap in the educational system that stems from the historical legacy of apartheid, as consequent, impeding adaptability. In a country like South Africa, where there are enormous variations in income and access to resources, Jantjies (2020) asserts that there is a need for the government to consider a multifaceted approach in delivering the curriculum to students. For some, online devices may be viable, while others will need to receive printed materials or tune into radio or TV lessons. However, one may assume that the impact may not be the same, thus hampering the success of inclusive education.

Discussion and recommendation

While online learning as a concept on paper presents more opportunities for inclusive education, it remains constrained by many challenges in South Africa. Through online learning, the physical/traditional classroom setup is not a requirement, thus eliminating all the previously existing barriers associated with the classroom setup, hence it may seem viable to shift the focus from

face to face classes to fully electronic/digital teaching and learning. In the context of South Africa, inclusive education via eLearning remains elusive. This paper reveals that the socio-economic outlook of South Africa is self-defeating. South Africa's basic education system remains overwhelmed by inequalities dating back to the apartheid era. Most of the country's pupils come from disadvantaged backgrounds. In poorer households, many children do not have a desk, books, internet connectivity, a computer, or parents to help facilitate home-schooling within the household. The disparity in access to digital devices and connectivity between rich and poor requires immediate attention. This will help mitigate the digital divide conundrum. COVID-19 has shown that technology is no longer a luxury but an important component of educational advancement. In presenting solutions, a wide range of factors must be considered. What should be prioritized is the socio-economic disparities that continue to negatively impact progress in the country.

Shenilla Mohamed, Executive Director of Amnesty International S.A states, "For South Africa to comply with both its own constitutional and international human rights obligations concerning education, major change is needed urgently". A lot still needs to be done in the country to break down the walls created by segregation. It is in this context that we argue that South Africa needs to facilitate inclusive development in its attempt to end economic class divisions, which will then help bridge the digital divide and reduce educational inequality. Until such a time, the notion of a successful online learning system in the country shall remain elusive until these underlying factors are achieved.

Conclusion

One cannot deny that COVID-19 has globally altered how education is undertaken and delivered. Globally, lockdowns have become the order of the day; this has, however, resulted in stagnant economic growth, insolvency and bankruptcy. Even though they have been beneficial to some extent, continual lockdowns are not the answer to bringing the pandemic under control. Countries across the world used lockdowns and social distancing measures to control the spread of the virus. This strategy, however, led to socio-economic woes in the country, such as widespread unemployment, business closures and poverty. In South Africa, Without COVID-19, the South African basic education department would not have engaged the importance and urgent need to develop a robust e-learning approach. Nevertheless, one cannot ignore the challenges of online

learning. Firstly, the unequal development of the education sector in South Africa needs to be addressed. Some schools, almost 25 years after multiparty politics still lack basic infrastructure, are still constructed out of mud and are in technologically secluded areas. Therefore, even if the government was to prioritize learner support interventions, the location of schools would become a barrier. Secondly, we posit that the use of technology is not inclined to pupils themselves but also educators. The pandemic has seen educators rushed into taking part in technological interventions (online learning) even though they had little time training in terms of its usage, this itself represents another challenge. And finally, we argue that the government did not anticipate the educational calamity as a result of the pandemic, and thus the pressure to finish the academic year and reduce the possibility of a huge failure rate to some extent disregarded the need to produce quality learners vested of knowledge development, especially in public sector schools.

Bibliography

- Amnesty International South Africa. (2020). South Africa: Broken and unequal education perpetuating poverty and inequality. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2020/South-Africa-broken-and-unequal-education-perpetuating-poverty-and-inequality>
- Abbasi S., Ayoob T., Malik A. & Memon S., Perceptions of students regarding E-learning during Covid-19 at a private medical college, Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7306963/>
- Bagarukayo E & Kalema B., (2015), Evaluation of Learning usage in South African Universities.A critical review. Vol. 11, Issue2, 168-183. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1074146.pdf>
- Burger, G. and Sinha,A., (2012). South African mobile generation: Study on South African young people on mobiles. UNICEF. https://www.unicef.org/csr/files/UNICEF_South_Africa_-_the_mobile_generation.pdf
- Burker, J., (2020). South Africa struggles to contain second Covid wave with new strain, The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/dec/22/south-africa-struggles-contain-second-covid-wave-new-strain>
- Czerniewicz L, Ravjee N & Mlitwa N. (2006). ICT's and the South African Higher Education Landscapes. Research Gate. <https://www.researchgate.net>3223>
- Department of Basic Education, (2020). School Recovery Plan in Response to Covid-19.

- <https://www.education.gov.za/Portals/0/Documents/Recovery%20plan%20page/Links%20for%20schools/school-recovery-plan-june-2020-1.pdf?ver=2020-06-15-091102-260>.
- Emmanuel, A.O., (2013), Effect of student-teacher ratio on students' academic performance in secondary schools in the Ado-Odo/Ota Local Government area of Ogun State, M.Ed. dissertation, National Open University of Nigeria, Lagos.
- Department of Health. (2020). South African Government. Department of Health. <https://www.gov.za/speeches/minister-zweli-mkhizi-confirms-total-29-240-cases-coronavirus-covid-19-29-may-2020-0000>.
- IOL, Reporter. (2020). Over 1 100 coronavirus cases in age group between 10 and 19 in SA. IOL News. <https://www.iol.co.za/news/south-africa/over-1-100-coronavirus-cases-in-age-group-between-10-and-19-in-sa-48668258>
- Isabirye, A. K. & Dlodlo, N. (2014). Perceived Inhibitors of Innovative E-Learning Teaching Practice at a South African University of Technology. Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, Vol 5, p390-398.
- Jantjies, M, (2020). How South Africa can address digital learning inequalities in e-learning. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/how-south-africa-can-address-digital-inequalities-in-e-learning-137086>
- Jantjies, M, (2020). What South Africa's teachers brought to the virtual classroom during COVID-19. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/what-south-africas-teachers-brought-to-the-virtual-classroom-during-covid-19-147306>
- Jaffer, S., N'gambi, D., & Czerniewicz, L. (2007). The role of ICTs in higher education in South Africa: One strategy for addressing teaching and learning challenges. International Journal of Education and ICT, Vol 3, p131-142.
- Kaylynn, P., (2020). Anxious, stressed South Africans really battling under lockdown, SADAG. <https://ewn.co.za/2020/05/07/anxious-stressed-south-africans-really-battling-under-lockdown-says-sadag>
- Kulkarni, P. (2020). Continued resistance to school reopening in South Africa. <https://peoplesdispatch.org/2020/06/03/continued-resistance-to-school-reopening-in-south-africa/>
- Mary, L., (2020). Coronavirus: what are asymptomatic and mild COVID-19?. Patient. <https://patient.info/news-and-features/coronavirus-what-are-asymptomatic-and-mild-covid-19>

- Microsoft in Education. (2014). Transforming Learning Environments for Anytime, Anywhere Learning for all: Transforming Framework. <https://www.microsoft.com/education/>
- Mlitwa, W. & Van Belle, J. W. G. D. (2011). Mediators for lecturer perspectives on learning management systems at universities in the Western Cape, South Africa. In Proceedings of the Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems (PACIS 2011), 2011, Brisbane, Australia. Brisbane: AIS Electronic Library.
- Moll, I., Adam, F., Backhouse, J., & Mhlang, E. (2007). Status Report on ICTs and Higher Education in South Africa, http://www.judybackhouse.com/pdfs/saide_status_of_elearning_in_sa.pdf
- O'Shaughnessy, M. and Stadler, J. 2008. Media and Society. Melbourne: Oxford University Press.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, (2011), Education at a glance: What is the student-teacher ratio and how big are classes?, OECD, <https://www.oecd.org/edu/skills-beyond-school/48631144.pdf>
- Peoples Dispatch. (2020). South African teachers' unions warn against reopening schools without proper precautions. <https://peoplesdispatch.org/2020/05/22/south-african-teachers-unions-warn-against-reopening-schools-without-proper-precautions/>
- Research ICT Africa and Intelcon, (2012). Mobile Usage at the Base of the Pyramid in South Africa. https://www.infodev.org/infodev-files/final_south_africa_bop_study_web.pdf
- Richards, S, E. (2020). Why do asymptomatic COVID-19 cases even happen?. <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/2020/07/why-do-asymptomatic-coronavirus-cases-even-happen-cvd/>
- South African Government. (2020). Minister Angie Motshekga: State of readiness for the return of the second cohort of grades back to school. <https://www.gov.za/speeches/minister-angie-motshekga-state-readiness-return-second-cohort-grades-back-school-5-jul-2020>
- Staff, W., (2020). South Africa expected to delay reopening of schools: report. <https://businesstech.co.za/news/government/403449/south-africa-expected-to-delay-reopening-of-schools-report/>
- Statista. (2021). Coronavirus (COVID-19) cases in South Africa as of October 24, 2021, by region.

- <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1108127/coronavirus-cases-in-south-africa-by-region/>
- Skelton, A., (2014), 'Leveraging funds for school infrastructure: The South African "mud schools" case study', in UKFIET international conference on education and development: Education and development post 2015: Reflecting, reviewing, reimagining., Oxford, https://www.norrag.org/fileadmin/Events/Oxford/OxCon_2013_Skelton.pdf
- Toyana, M., (2020). Explainer: The new coronavirus variant in South Africa - Are concerns justified?, Yahoo news. <https://news.yahoo.com/explainer-coronavirus-variant-south-africa-073927103.html>
- Walker, A. (2019), Just 10.4% of South African households have direct access to the internet, Memeburn. <https://memeburn.com/2019/05/south-africa-internet-users-2018/>
- Zelda, V., (2020). IOL News. <https://www.iol.co.za/pretoria-news/educators-union-of-sa-heads-to-court-wants-schools-to-remain-closed-48847778>
- Zhang, Y. 2006. Urban-Rural Literacy Gaps in Sub-Saharan Africa: The Roles of Socioeconomic Status and School Quality. University of Chicago Press Journal. Vol. 50, No. 4. Pp581-602.
- Gulati, S. (2008). Technology-enhanced learning in developing nations: A review. International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning, 9(1), p1–16.